

Deliverable D6.3

Project Title:	Building data bridges between biological and medical infrastructures in Europe	
Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
Grant agreement no.:	284209	
	Research Infrastructures, FP7 Capacities Specific Programme; [INFRA-2011-2.3.2.] "Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of "Life sciences"	
Deliverable title:	List of standards and ontologies in human image data sets	
WP No.	6	
Lead Beneficiary:	16: UH	
WP Title	Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales	
Contractual delivery date:	31 December 2013	
Actual delivery date:	23 December 2013	
WP leader:	Jan Ellenberg	1: EMBL
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	16: UH	

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1 Executive summary

A list of the most relevant standards and ontologies used for cell- and tissue-level human image data has been produced. The list is mainly focused on cell- and tissue images acquired by microscopy imaging.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Demonstrate the utility of the interoperability of large-scale image data sets from different biological scales (cell – tissue – organism)		x
2	Enable comparison of morphological image data of cellular phenotypes of individual genes with morphological image data of the diseased tissues in mouse and human	x	
3	Link imaging data with molecular data, including cancer genome sequences and cancer expression data		x

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

As part of the work towards mapping between different image data sets, a list of the most relevant standards and ontologies used for human image data has been produced. The list is currently focused on cell- and tissue images acquired by microscopy imaging and does not include standards and ontologies developed for other imaging modalities (X-ray, CT, MRI, US etc).

Standards for the exchange of human microscopy-level tissue image data include the work towards Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM), Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE) and Health Level 7 (HL7).

DICOM includes 27 working groups and anyone with a material interest may participate. Version 3 of the DICOM standard was released in 1992.

DICOM is a communication, high-level, conceptual standard that facilitates interchange, but does not mandate internal storage formats for example within a PACS system. Image object definitions are central and the standard is widely adopted in radiology and addresses workflow as well as images.

Microscopy image data of human samples (mainly pathology images) presents specific challenges and opportunities to DICOM. In particular:

1. Some pathology-related image formats do not as yet have applicable DICOM Information Object Definitions. Examples include whole slide images, high-order multi-spectral images, flow cytometry, electron microscopy and others.
2. Many pathology processes provide challenges in distinguishing "objective" image data from "interpretive" image information. These challenges will include specifying standards for pathology-specific mark-up that would reliably distinguish "unprocessed" from "processes" image data, image annotations from primary image data and "constructed" images from "raw" images, etc.

A working group (no 26) within DICOM on pathology image data was formed in 2005 and has representatives from most major pathology imaging vendors and includes also pathologists, consultants and researchers, a total of 60+ organizations from more than 10 countries.

Supplement (no 122) to the DICOM standard was approved in 2008. It specifies a specimen description model which allows description of: a) Type of specimen b) Procurement and processing steps c) Sampling methods and d) Physical attributes of slides. However, Supplement 122 does not provide the ability to identify subregions of a slide/block, staining and fixation information is often co-mingled and specimen descriptions difficult to parse out from large text blocks. Dictionaries and ontologies may also be poorly implemented. In

conclusion, the DICOM standard for human microscopy-level image data is still a work in progress.

Future work items within the DICOM include a) Structured Reports and/or Evidence Documents in Pathology involving full demographic information; b) Correlation of radiologic and pathologic images, including image-guided biopsies; c) Coding information based upon existing WHO codification, SNOMED-CT and also ADICAP thesaurus; d) Navigating in a hierarchy of images by means of annotations of images and/or drawings (e.g. gross imaging annotated with the localization of the blocks); e) Dealing with Tissue Micro Arrays (one slide for hundreds of patients) with a link to patient information; f) Integration of automated image analysis tools with whole-slide images.

The IHE Anatomic Pathology¹ addresses information sharing, workflow and patient care in Pathology, including anatomical pathology.

IHE Anatomic Pathology integration profiles are specified in detail in the IHE Anatomic Pathology Technical Framework. These profiles include:

1. Anatomic Pathology Workflow (APW) integrates the pathology department in the healthcare institution and covers these specialties: surgical pathology, clinical autopsy, cytopathology.
2. Anatomic Pathology Reporting to Public Health (ARPH) transmits anatomic pathology reports to public health organizations (cancer registries, centers for disease control, screening organizations, etc.).
3. Anatomic Pathology Structured Report (APSR) provides templates for building surgical pathology reports (cancers, benign neoplasms as well as non-neoplastic conditions).

The Anatomic Pathology group of HL7. The mission of the Anatomic Pathology working group is to develop and review implementation guides of HL7 standards and to enhance existing HL7 standards to support anatomic pathology use cases.

It will work within HL7 as well as with external organizations to facilitate information interoperability in anatomic pathology, such as: a) Tracking of anatomic pathology specimens; b) Structuring and coding of anatomic

¹ http://www.ihe.net/Anatomic_Pathology/

reports; c) Integrating and consolidating anatomic pathology data and other data into the medical record (e.g. integrated composite reports); d) Ensuring consistency of anatomic pathology data and corresponding image association (includes both radiology and pathology imaging); e) Reviewing previously defined terms that differ between organizations (e.g. What is a “specimen”); f) Developing/reviewing value sets as needed (e.g. DICOM Specimen Embedding Media); e) Collecting and sharing data from biorepositories/tissue banks.

3.2 Ontologies for human image data sets

- Terminologies and ontologies for annotation of human image data sets include: Human Phenotype Ontology
- Terminologica Histologica
- Terminologica Embryologica
- Human Developmental Anatomy
- International Classification of Diseases (ICD)
- SNOMED CT
- The BRENDA Tissue Ontology

In addition, many cross-references to human image data are available in Mouse Phenotype EMAP, Edinburgh and MP Mouse Phenotype ontologies.

A short summary of the ontologies for human cell- and tissue level image data:

Human Phenotype Ontology

- Aims to provide a standardized vocabulary of phenotypic abnormalities encountered in human disease.
- Charite Berlin, University of Cambridge, MRC Harwell, Berkley Bioinformatics and Ontology Project (BBOP), ACHSE e.V.
- <http://www.human-phenotype-ontology.org>
- <http://compbio.charite.de/phenomizer/>
- Mapped to OMIM
- Reference: Köhler S et al. The Human Phenotype Ontology project: linking molecular biology and disease through phenotype data Nucleic Acids Res. 2013 Nov 11. [Epub ahead of print]

Terminologia Histologica

- Human histology and cytology
- published by the Federative International Programme on Anatomical Terminologies (FIPAT)
- Available in a book format and online as pdf (facsimile)
- An electronic version has been created at FIMM this year
- Reference: Terminologia Histologica 2008. Wolters Kluwer Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, ISBN: 978-0-7817-7537-3

Terminologia Embryologica

- a standardized list of words used in the description of human embryologic and fetal structures
- produced by the Federative International Committee on Anatomical Terminology on behalf of the International Federation of Associations of Anatomists
- <http://www.unifr.ch/ifaa/Public/EntryPage/ViewSource.html>
- Reference: Terminologia Embryologica. Published by Thieme. ISBN (Americas): 9783131701411

Human Developmental Anatomy

- A structured controlled vocabulary of stage-specific anatomical structures of the human
- It has been designed to mesh with the mouse anatomy and incorporates each Carnegie stage of development (CS1-20).
- Each term is mentioned only once so that the embryo at each stage can be seen as the simple sum of its parts.
- Bioinformatics Group, Division of Biomedical Sciences, Hugh Robson Building, University of Edinburgh, UK.
- Part of the OBO foundry
- Reference: Hunter A, Kaufman MH, McKay A, Baldock R, Simmen MW, Bard JB. An ontology of human developmental anatomy. J Anat. 2003 Oct;203(4):347-55.

International Classification of Diseases (ICD)

- published by WHO

- codes for diseases, signs and symptoms, abnormal findings, complaints, social circumstances, and external causes of injury or diseases
- ICD 10 contains basic morphology codes that can be suitable for tissue annotation
- The code set allows more than 14,400 different codes and permits the tracking of many new diagnoses. The codes can be expanded to over 16,000 codes by using optional sub-classifications.
- <http://www.who.int/classifications/icd/en/>

SNOMED CT

- SNOMED Clinical Terms (CT) is a systematically organized computer processable collection of medical terms providing codes, terms, synonyms and definitions used in clinical documentation and reporting
- is considered to be the most comprehensive, multilingual clinical healthcare terminology in the world
- can cross-map to other international standards and classifications
- SNOMED M (morphology) is part of the SNOMED CT and intended for disease related morphologies and used for example in oncology as part of the ICD-O-3 terminology
- <http://www.ihtsdo.org/snomed-ct/>

The BRENDA Tissue Ontology

- Represents a comprehensive structured encyclopedia of tissue terms.
- A connection between the enzyme data collection of the BRENDA enzyme database and a structured network of source tissues and cell types
- Currently, BTO contains more than 4600 different anatomical structures, tissues, cell types and cell lines, conforms with Gene Ontology Consortium and organized as a directed acyclic graph (DAG).
- <http://www.BTO.brenda-enzymes.org>
- Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institute for Bioinformatics and Biochemistry, Langer Kamp 19 B, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany.
- Reference: Gremse M, Chang A, Schomburg I, Grote A, Scheer M, Ebeling C, Schomburg D. The BRENDA Tissue Ontology (BTO): the

first all-integrating ontology of all organisms for enzyme sources.
Nucleic Acids Res. 2011;39:D507-13

4 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5 Adjustments made

Eight person-months were transferred to deliverable 6.5 Prediction of novel cancer biomarkers (e.g. breast and prostate cancer). No person-months originally reserved for this by a mistake in the budget, although UH/FIMM is listed as a contributor.

6 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 6; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 6 Title: Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales

Lead: Jan Ellenberg (EMBL)
Participants: EMBL, HMGU, CIRMMP

Work package number	WP6	Start date or starting event:	month 13	
Work package title	PhenoBridge-crossing the species bridge between mouse and human			
Activity Type	RTD			
Participant number	1:EMBL	11:HMGU	20: CIRMMP	
Person-months per participant	37	27	16	

Objectives

This work package will demonstrate the utility of the interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales (cell – tissue – organism) to enable drug target and biomarker discovery for human disease with cancer as an example. Based on the standards and services developed in WP2 and 3, we will use integrated access to systematic imaging data of disease gene function in cultured human cells (EMBL-Heidelberg) and systematic imaging data available from tissue microarrays of diseased tissue from both human patients (FIMM, U Helsinki) and mouse models (HMGU).

This use case will thus link the four BMS ESFRI infrastructures Euro-BioImaging (EMBL-Heidelberg), BMRI (U Helsinki), EATRIS (U Helsinki-FIMM) and Infrafrontier (HMGU) with the standards and services provided by ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI) and require strong links to ELIXIR's molecular data resources. The comparison of morphological image data on cellular phenotypes of individual genes, with morphological image data of the diseased tissues in mouse models and human patients could create a powerful predictor of optimized biomarkers as well as drug targets in cancer. Linking these imaging data with molecular data including the cancer genome sequence and cancer expression data, will allow in silico validation of the predictions and prioritization of biomarkers for validation in clinical research.

Description of work and role of participants

Task 1.1. Implementation of interoperability standards and ontologies for reference image data sets

(Leader: U. Helsinki-FIMM, Participants: EMBL-Heidelberg, U Helsinki, EMBL-EBI, HMGU)

The first task to make integrated image data access usable is to map the (meta)data standards and ontologies present within each image data domain (cell, human and mouse tumor tissue) onto each other to enable correlative analysis. In line with the standards and services developed in WP2, 3 and where applicable respecting the secure access to medical data developed in WP4, we will implement unambiguous maps between the respective metadata. For this we will select high throughput imaging reference data sets with cancer related assays (e.g. www.mitocheck.org, www.cellmigration.org/resource/discovery/#genes) as well as tumor tissue and clinical data (we will make these available at: fimm.webmicroscope.net/)

Task 1.2. Prediction of novel cancer biomarkers (e.g. breast and prostate cancer) (Leader: EMBL-Heidelberg, Participants: FIMM, U Helsinki, HMGU, EMBL-EBI).

Correlative analysis of interoperable cell and tissue image datasets with their associated annotation and metadata will be mined with state of the art bioinformatic tools to predict novel biomarker candidates. In particular we will focus on genes with function in cell cycle and cell division control as well as invasive behavior, for which comprehensive molecular and cellular datasets are available. An initial set of predicted biomarkers will then be further cross-validated against the biomolecular databases hosted by ELIXIR, drawing on cancer genome and expression data, as well as general sequence and structural properties of the identified genes to also explore their potential as drug targets.

7 Attachments

The slide features a dark blue background with a pattern of light blue dots that create a sense of depth and perspective. In the top left corner, the FIMM logo is displayed, including the text 'FIMM Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland Nordic EMBL Partnership for Molecular Medicine'. In the top right corner, the BioMedBridges logo is shown. A central orange box contains the title 'D6.3 List of standards and ontologies in human image data sets'. Below this, the name and title of the research director, Johan Lundin, are listed. At the bottom, there is a small copyright notice and the website address.

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Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland
Nordic EMBL Partnership for Molecular Medicine

BioMedBridges

D6.3 List of standards and ontologies in human image data sets

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Univ. of Helsinki

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Potential ontologies and standards for human image data sets

- › Human Phenotype Ontology
- › Terminologica Histologica
- › Terminologica Embryologica
- › Human Developmental Anatomy
- › International Classification of Diseases (ICD)
- › SNOMED CT
- › The BRENDA Tissue Ontology
- › Mouse Phenotype EMAP, Edinburgh and MP Mouse Phenotype

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Human Phenotype Ontology

Nucleic Acids Research Advance Access published November 11, 2013

Nucleic Acids Research, 2013, 1–9
doi:10.1093/nar/gkt11026

The Human Phenotype Ontology project: linking molecular biology and disease through phenotype data

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Terminologia Histologica

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Terminologia Histologica

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

The **Terminologia Histologica** (TH) is a controlled vocabulary for use in cytology and histology.^{[1][2]} In April 2011, Terminologia Histologica was published online [by](#) the Federative International Programme on Anatomical Terminologies (FIPAT), the successor of FCAT.

It was intended to replace *Nomina Histologica*. The *Nomina Histologica* was introduced in 1977, with the fourth edition of *Nomina Anatomica*.^[3]

It was developed by the Federative International Committee on Anatomical Terminology.

Outline [\[edit\]](#)

- h1.00: Cytology [1] [↗](#)
- h2.00: General histology [2] [↗](#)
 - H2.00.01.0.00001: Stem cells [3] [↗](#)
 - H2.00.02.0.00001: Epithelial tissue [4] [↗](#)
 - H2.00.02.0.01001: Epithelial cell
 - H2.00.02.0.02001: Surface epithelium
 - H2.00.02.0.03001: Glandular epithelium
 - H2.00.03.0.00001: Connective and supportive tissues [5] [↗](#)
 - H2.00.03.0.01001: Connective tissue cells
 - H2.00.03.0.02001: Extracellular matrix
 - H2.00.03.0.03001: Fibres of connective tissues
 - H2.00.03.1.00001: Connective tissue proper
 - H2.00.03.1.01001: Ligaments

16/12/2013
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